

Final Report

Hyperspectral algorithm development and dimension reduction for improved detection of shallow coastal submerged vegetation

Jackson State University (*FY2008 Initiated Project*)

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Abstract

The accomplishments, participants and their contributions, and the research results and outcomes of the NURI project, hyperspectral algorithm development and dimension reduction for improved detection of shallow coastal submerged vegetation, are presented in this final report. The project started on October 7, 2008 and has been completed. The research team at Jackson State University conducted a series of studies during the project period to accomplish the following tasks: modeling and developing algorithm to remove overlying water effects to improve benthic mapping; mathematically extending the depth or turbidity limits for detection of submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV); identifying critical spectral information for data compression; calibrating and validating the algorithm using airborne hyperspectral data; developing graphical user interface for each implementation of algorithm by end users.

Key Words: Submerged Aquatic Vegetation (SAV), water effect correction, remote sensing, coastal benthic mapping, GUI

1.0 Executive Summary

The overarching research goal of the project was to advance the usages and applications of remote sensing data in studies of shallow aquatic/coastal environment and its biological resources by developing broadly applicable index which will efficiently allow detection/classification of submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV)/seagrass. The specific objectives included development of hyperspectral algorithms that: (1) decompose the composite signals from a remote sensing dataset into its primary components: vegetation, water depth, and turbidity; (2) reduce the water effects in order to extend the depth or turbidity limits of detection of seagrass; and (3) identify critical spectral information for data compression that does not compromise the ability of constructing geometry of SAV beds.

During the project years, we have collected and compiled extensive experimental and *in-situ* spectral signals of various aquatic plants at varying water depths and under varying turbidity levels in order to find spectral regions that are sensitive to vegetation. We experimentally tested if the conventionally used vegetation indices could be used to depict canopies of aquatic plants in shallow waters. When corrected for water attenuation using the data obtained from our experiments, the index values can significantly improve if information on spectral reflectance attenuation caused by water volume increases is collected simultaneously through ground-truthing and integrated. We also used an experimental approach to model volumetric scattering and absorption of water (% of the total incident radiation) by empirically separating the energy absorbed by water and scattered from the water column using an indoor water tank with hypothetical surfaces that either reflect or absorb all the incoming light. Using the experimental data, a function was developed to correct reflectance measured from a shallow water body for the water effects. When applied to independently measured reflectance of underwater vegetation; the algorithm significantly enhanced vegetation signals, especially in near infrared (NIR).

The water correction algorithm was then implemented as a module that can be called from the ENVI's programming environment using a Graphical User Interface (GUI) that we developed. The water correction module was added as a function call under the ENVI's main menu bar so that the user can simply locate and select the option in order to call and use the module. Under the current module and the GUI, users are able to select water depth (0 – 1.0 m) and turbidity (0-20 NTU) using slide bars, for which (a) given hyperspectral band(s) can be corrected. The corrected reflectance can be generated and compared to the original one at either a given pixel, within a small subset; and the original and corrected images can be displayed.

Our study suggest that: (1) The experimentally driven algorithm significantly improved the vegetation signals, especially in the NIR regions; (2) The algorithm also improved mapping capabilities of dense seagrass beds in shallow, clear water; and (3) The algorithm application will be user-friendly and versatile if the current module and GUI are improved with more optical parameters included in, calibrated, and validated the model.

2.0 Introduction

2.1 Status of the grant, summary of results and progress

The two-year project started on October 7th, 2008. The overarching research goal is to advance the usages and applications of remote sensing data in studies of shallow aquatic/coastal environment and its biological resources by developing broadly applicable index which will efficiently allow detection/classification of submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV)/seagrass. The specific objectives include development of hyperspectral algorithms that: (1) decompose the composite signals from a remote sensing dataset into its primary components: vegetation, water depth, and turbidity; (2) reduce the water effects in order to extend the depth or turbidity limits of detection of seagrass; and (3) identify critical spectral information for data compression that does not compromise the ability of constructing geometry of SAV beds.

During the first project year, we have collected and compiled extensive experimental and *in-situ* spectral signals of various aquatic plants at varying water depths and under varying turbidity levels in order to find spectral regions that are sensitive to vegetation. We experimentally tested if the conventionally used vegetation indices can be used to depict canopies of aquatic plants in shallow waters. When corrected for water attenuation using the data obtained from our experiments, the index values can significantly improve if information on spectral reflectance attenuation caused by water volume increases is collected simultaneously through ground-truthing and integrated (Cho *et al.* 2008).

We also used an experimental approach to model volumetric scattering and absorption of water (% of the total incident radiation) (Cho and Lu, *in press*) by empirically separating the energy absorbed by water and scattered from the water column using an indoor water tank with hypothetical surfaces that either reflect or absorb all the incoming light. Using the experimental data, a function was developed to correct reflectance measured from a shallow water body for the water effects. When applied to independently measured reflectance of underwater vegetation; the algorithm significantly enhanced vegetation signals, especially in near infrared (NIR).

We conducted ground-truth surveys of seagrass distributions during flyover campaigns in conjunction with aerial hyperspectral data collections in 2008 at Mission-Aransas National Estuarine Research Reserve, TX and in 2009 at Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve, MS. These field campaigns were supported by the NGA grants (HM1582-08-1-0049; HM1582-07-1-2005) as well as a National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) grant. The aforementioned experimentally-driven algorithm was applied to the image data; it improved mapping capabilities and classification of seagrass beds by partially restoring the NIR signals from the benthic vegetation.

To study compression methods for image data, we conducted a performance evaluation on DCT (Discrete Cosine Transform) and wavelet-based compression methods. These two methods have been utilized at international standards for image and/or multimedia data compression, as well as widely used in Internet and/or multimedia applications. However, little research has been done on their performance over remote sensing images or hyperspectral data. Thus, our study was conducted to investigate how the two methods work on remote sensing images, and which method produces a better performance.

We also studied and applied data mining techniques over the collected experimental data to investigate significant spectral bands respect to aquatic plants. To decompose the signals into the primary components, and to identify the critical spectral bands for data compression, an extensive study over characteristics of reflectance and effects of the primary components at each band under different environments should be conducted. We found that IDT (Iterative Denosing Tree) and Incomparable Sensors, developed by Center for Imaging Science at Johns Hopkins University, are promising for our study, and findings by utilizing these two methods over the experimental data are presented in this report.

2.2 Participants and contributions

Besides the three principal investigators (J. Cho, H. Kim, and C. Wafosoh), Duanjun Lu, a Ph.D. student of Environmental Science and Research Associate of Department of Physics at JSU, participated in the project in modeling of water column scattering and absorption. Philemon Kirui, a Ph.D. student of Environmental Science Program, has been participating in the project by conducting controlled experiments and field data collection. He is expected to produce a Ph.D. dissertation as an outcome. The NGA funds have been used to support his experiments and trips to the field sites and conferences. Two master's students have been receiving stipends directly from the NURI grant: Marvin Washington of Department of Mathematics and Gibel Gaye of Department of Computer Science. They both started the M.S. programs in fall 2009; Marvin Washington has been involved in the project since December 2008 as an undergraduate research assistant. Marvin has been working to employ Radial Basis Function Interpolation to extrapolate underwater signal values at deeper depths; filtering and interpolating experimental data to reduce noises; and spectral mixing of the water and vegetation signals. Gibel started in July 2009 and is expected to produce a M.S. thesis on hyperspectral data feature selection and data reduction. Prior to Gibel, we had six student candidates who applied for the assistant position. We selected one of the candidates, but the student had to resign from the assistantship after two months (February and March of 2009) due to personal reasons.

3.0 Background

3.1 The problem being addressed

Remote sensing has significantly advanced spatial analyses on terrestrial vegetation for various fields of science. The distinctive spectral characteristics of the green plants, low reflectance in the visible light and high reflectance in near-infrared (NIR), has been used to develop spectral indices such as Simple Vegetation Index ($SVI = NIR \text{ reflectance} - \text{red reflectance}$) and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index ($NDVI = (NIR \text{ reflectance} - \text{red reflectance}) / (NIR \text{ reflectance} + \text{red reflectance})$) for depicting and classifying vegetation. The vegetation spectral indices are simple but versatile and can be used to compare data obtained under varying illumination conditions. However, the conventional vegetation indices may not be effectively used for plants that grow underwater or that are temporarily flooded (Beget and Di Bella 2007) because the water overlying the vegetation canopies reduces the vegetation effects of 'red absorption' and the 'NIR reflectance' (Han and Rundquist 2003, Cho 2007, Cho *et al.* 2008).

Submerged Aquatic Vegetation (SAV) is a group of vascular plants that grows underwater. SAV includes seagrass species that play a vital role in the ecological processes/dynamics/productivity

of shallow coastal and marine ecosystems. On the other hand, freshwater SAV can become invasive in nutrient-rich inland water bodies by forming extensive canopies that interfere with light penetration, hinder navigation & recreational activities, and harm fisheries.

Although remotely sensed data have been used to produce cost-effective and spatially repetitive information on underwater vegetation distribution and abundance, mapping of SAV using satellite data has focused on classifications based on signal variations in the multi-spectral bands, especially those in the short visible wavelengths with high water penetration (Maeder *et al.* 2002, Pasqualini *et al.* 2005); and the NIR region was often not used due to its high attenuation in water. However, NIR reflectance serves as the primary cue for discriminating vegetation type and as the critical component for the widely used vegetation indices.

Differentiation of the SAV spectral signature from bare substrate or algae is further limited in shallow coastal waters that are more turbid than open ocean waters due to higher levels of phytoplankton, suspended sediment, and dissolved color. Upwelling signals from water bodies contain several components including reflectance from water surface, water column (suspended matter), and bottom backscattering (SAV and substrate) (Spitzer and Dirks 1987). Therefore, SAV-detecting-algorithms that reduce depth effects and that minimizes impact of turbidity and dissolved color need to be developed. The vertical water column thickness between the canopy top and the water surface does not usually exceed a half to one meter during the peak growing season. If algorithms that reduce the shallow overlying water effects are applied to correct the reflectance signals from SAV beds, the vegetation signals in the NIR would be partially restored even in mildly turbid waters.

Increased availability of airborne- or spaceborne-hyperspectral sensors and data would improve remote detection and mapping of underwater objects. While hyperspectral data provide detailed information that can be derived from the fine-scaled variations in narrow spectral bands, the enormous size and increased dimension of the datasets make it hard to process. Furthermore, hyperspectral data provides redundant information and potentially contain large errors/noises that will further complicate analyses and interpretation. Therefore, data mining and feature extraction/analysis should be preceded in order to reduce the data dimension without sacrificing ability to detect SAV signal and to classify based on the probability of potentially containing SAV. This will help achieve our goal to develop a successful index/algorithm for SAV detection and probability.

3.2 Why is it important

Submerged Aquatic Vegetation (SAV) is a vital component of ecological processes/dynamics/productivity of coastal ecosystems. Healthy SAV beds help reduce wave energy, enhance sedimentation, stabilize sediment, provide fisheries habitat, and serve as a food source for wildlife (Orth and Moore 1984). Information on SAV distribution, composition, and abundance is widely used as an indicator of aquatic environmental quality, but remote detection of this underwater vegetation has been limited as described in the previous section. Our research aims to improve and advance remote sensing of SAV in relatively turbid, depth-varying coastal environment through developing SAV-detecting-algorithms that reduce depth effects and that minimize impact of turbidity and dissolved color. More importantly, we will develop a widely applicable vegetation index that indicates probability of SAV occurrence, which will be a novel way to classify and to map benthic habitat. The practical importance of the outcome in coastal restoration is significant because it is vital to include potential SAV habitat area, not only the

densely vegetated beds, in successful restoration planning (Cho and Poirrier 2005). Unfortunately, conservation efforts are generally given only to the areas with actual SAV beds; and the restricted conservation would likely cause further degradation of potential habitat.

Research relationship with NGA-supported topics: Our research is closely related to the following three topics that support the overall objectives of the 2008 Broad Agency Announcement (BAA) by National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency (NGA): to enhance the capabilities of U.S. universities to perform research in geospatial science topics that are important for geospatial intelligence and, in conjunction with that research, provide education in related science and engineering areas that are important for U.S. national security.

- Topic 2.3 Advanced Dimension Reduction and Categorization
- Topic 3.4 Biologically-Inspired Computer Vision for Multiband Data
- Topic 4.3 Analytic Tools and Techniques for Geospatial Information Science

3.3 What is the state-of-the-art/state-of-the-practice

Leverage from other research projects: (1) algorithm development and modeling based on our own field and experimental data; and (2) corresponding ground-truth data collected along with image data will be used.

Biologically-meaningful classification: (1) use of both spectral and spatial information to develop a widely applicable vegetation index that indicates “probability” of SAV occurrence, which will be a novel way to classify and to map benthic habitat; and (2) maximization of information gathered from all possible sources (field research and real-world experiences), not only from digital data or purely mathematical models.

Practical application of the proposed research results: The research results will be linked with those of our other funded projects and directly applied to practical management/conservation activities such as delineating potential habitat for (i) coastal restoration, (ii) commercially/ecologically important seagrass dependent organisms, (iii) estimation of the current function provided by existing seagrass beds; (iv) invasive aquatics in inland water bodies; and (iv) projection of future changes (decline of favorable seagrass beds or expansion of invasive aquatics) that may occur with long-term environmental changes.

Computational advancement/innovation:

(1) IDT (Iterative Denosing Tree) and context-based clustering: The IDT approach, developed recently by researchers of Center for Imaging Science (CIS) at Johns Hopkins University, applies Principal Component Analysis (PCA) multiple times to identify outliers and preserve context information. A dimension reduction can be easily applied to the original data at various levels during the process without compromising data integrity. The result from the IDT is then used for model-based clustering so as to identify similarity and dissimilarity among the data. Research results from this approach have shown that the performance is much better comparing to other PCA-based approaches. Also, this approach can be applied to any type of data, such as hyperspectral data, image and audio data, data produced from social activities, etc. One of the co-PIs spent last summer at CIS to study this novel approach, applied the method to data from Open Source Software Development activities, and a research paper was published in Proceedings of the 2009 International Conference on Software Engineering Research and Practice (Kim et al. 2009). In addition,

the concept of Incomparable Sensors will be applied over the experimental data and the ground-truth data so as to study and/or measure the level of data integrity as well as the confidence of the research outputs.

- (2) Radial Basis Function (RBF) interpolation: RBF interpolation was introduced in land survey to solve the following problem: given few land marks on a given landscape, can we reconstruct the landscape. The solution of such problem enable for instance to find points with same elevation without going on the field to take measurements. RBF have been applied successfully in several field such as image reconstruction, flow simulation, artificial intelligence etc. The main attractive features of RBF interpolation is that it produces smooth interpolant and the computational effort is independent of the dimension of the data. In our project, we are going to use RBF to interpolate denoised remote sensing data. Using the smooth interpolant obtained and techniques from calculus/geometry (derivatives, curvature), to find a unique signature of marine vegetation. Assume for instance that our experimental data is made of reflectance (R), wavelength (w) and depth (d). We may use RBF interpolation to express $R = f(w,d)$. Preliminary results show that marine vegetation are characterized by high curvature on the surface $R=f(w,d)$. Such point with high curvature can be found using standard optimization algorithms. In addition, RBF interpolation will allow us to extrapolate remote sensing data especially for regions where such data is not readily available.

3.4 Capability weakness or shortfalls

Since our models/algorithms have been and will be developed based on experimental/field data, not through a purely computational approach, obtaining clean datasets that do not include significant environmental noises, human-caused errors, and impacts of external factors have been a challenge. Also, the 2009 airborne hyperspectral data, collected and preprocessed by CALMIT (Center for Agriculture and Land Management Information and Technology) at the University of Lincoln, Nebraska, have been severely defected by sun glints and detector failures. Additional airborne data collection is scheduled May 2010, to compensate this loss.

4.0 Technical Approach

4.1 Experimental Procedures

Reflectance data were measured over controlled (both indoor and outdoor tanks) experimental setting using a hand-held spectroradiometer. For the outdoor measurements, close range spectral measurements of downwelling and upwelling energy were made over outdoor tanks that contained floating/emergent waterhyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*), submerged species (*Myriophyllum aquaticum*, *Cabomba caroliniana*, and *Ceratophyllum demersum*), or over the tanks that contained only water without the vegetation. Spectral measurements were made on clear skies at near solar noon to minimize variability of solar elevation. For the indoor measurements, close-range spectral measurements of upwelling energy were made in a dark room over an experimental water tank using artificial lights (300 W reflector bulbs).

To obtain the depth-induced variations in the spectral responses of SAV, a mixture of *M. aquaticum*, *C. demersum* and *C.caroliniana* was threaded through a black mesh sheet and fixed on the bottom of a black-lined tank. The plants were planted at a density similar to the mean

natural density during the local growing season. The inside of the tanks were lined with black plastic pond liners or painted in black to eliminate reflectance from the interior surface. The tank was initially filled to the top using clear city tap water, then the water was continuously siphoned out with upwelling spectral measurements taken every 1.0cm in water-depth change until canopy level (10-20cm) was reached. As the water level is lowered, the sensor head was also lowered to keep a constant distance between water surface and the sensor.

Spectral measurements were also made over varying water depths using substitute bottoms instead of vegetation. The tank (70 cm tall with a diameter of 50 cm) interior walls were painted with a flat black water-insoluble color to minimize erroneous reflectance. Black-, white-, and gray-painted wooden panels that were cut to fit the bottom of the tank were used as surrogate bottoms to represent the hypothetical reflectance of 0 % and 100 %, respectively. Three 1.0 m-long supporting poles were painted in black and fixed to the edge of either black or white bottom at 120° apart from each other to maintain the balance when moved vertically. This device was slowly lowered into the tank filled with clear tap water (true color of < 5 mg/L Platinum Cobalt Scale (Pt Co); turbidity = 0 Nephelometric Turbidity Unit (NTU)). The upwelling radiance from the tank was scanned with a spectroradiometer (GER 1500™, Spectra Vista Corporation) with the fiber optic sensor fixed at 10 cm above the water surface to avoid any extraneous shadows or direct reflection of the light source. The instantaneous field of view of the optic fiber was 25°, resulting in 4.4 cm of sensor field of view on the water surface. Spectral measurements were made at 5 cm intervals between the depths of 70 cm and 15 cm, and then at every 1 cm thereafter until the water depth above the panel reached 0 cm. The same measurements were taken over waters with varying turbidity values.

The measured upwelling energy was then converted to reflectance (%) using the reference scan values measured prior to each set of data collection from a white Spectralon® panel which has a calibrated reflectance of approximately 99%. All reflectance values were calculated only between 400-900 nm to eliminate low signal-to-noise data, which resulted in data for 315 bands (Each band width ranges from 1.5-1.7 nm).

4.2. Image and *in situ* data collection

Study Areas: *In situ* data were obtained over seagrass beds in Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve (NERR) and Mission-Aransas NERR, TX. Grand Bay NERR is a protected area located in the southeastern Mississippi (30.41° 88.53° W) in Jackson County. It was established in 1999, encompassing 74.5 sq kilometers and managed by a partnership of local, state and federal agencies to promote estuarine research and education within the state coastal zone and its adjacent ecosystems. Among the bays and bayous located within the site include Middle bay, Pt. Aux Chenes Bay, Bayou Heron and Bayou Cumbest. Mission-Aransas NERR is bounded by the community of Rockport, Aransas Pass, Port Aransas and Ingleside. Submerged aquatic vegetation (seagrass) beds are estimated to cover an area of about 53 km², unlike other bays around the Gulf of Mexico, Corpus Christi has seen an increase in the area of seagrass beds, partially due to the rising sea levels that flooded former tidal flats, which allowed seagrass to develop. Texas Parks and Wildlife Fisheries Coastal Division (TPWD) has also played an important role in providing education and enforcing regulation that have greatly contributed to the protection of seagrass.

Image data acquisition: Aerial hyperspectral data were obtained in June 2009 over Grand Bay NERR and in July 2008 at Mission-Aransas NERR, TX. The data were obtained by AISA Eagle

hyperspectral sensor by the University of Nebraska at Lincoln's Center for Advanced Land Management Information Technologies (CALMIT); and the data were available through CALMIT after pre-processed for atmospheric and geographic corrections. The AISA Eagle is a complete, push broom system, consisting of a hyperspectral sensor head, miniature GPS/INS sensor, and data acquisition unit in a rugged PC with display unit and power supply. The image data had 63 hyperspectral bands within a range from 401 to 971 nm.

The following table identifies the general specifications for the AISA Eagle (Table 1). http://www.calmit.unl.edu/champ/aisa_eagle.php

Table 1. The general specification of the AISA Eagle.

Sensor Head	Typical specifications		
Spectrograph	High efficiency transmissive imaging spectrograph. Throughput practically independent of polarization. Smile and keystone < 5 microns.		
F/#	F/2.4		
Spectral Range	400-970 nm		
Spectral Pixels	244		
Spectral Sampling/Pixel	2.3 nm		
Slit Width	30 microns		
Spectral Resolution	2.9nm		
Fore optics	Standard	Optional	
	17 mm	23 mm	10 mm
FOV	39.7°	29.9°	63°
IFOV	0.039°	0.029°	0.062°
Ground Resolution @ 1000m	0.71 m	0.52 m	1.2 m
Camera	Progressive scan CCD camera		
Output	12 bits digital		
Integration Time	Settable independent of image rate		
Shutter	Electromechanical shutter for dark background registration, user controllable by software.		

FODIS	Diffuse light collector and fiber optic cable (5 m standard) with SMA connector.
Calibration	Sensor head comes with wavelength and radiometric calibration file.
Image Rate	Up to 50 images/s @ 244 hyperspectral bands. Up to 80 images/s @ 60 hyperspectral bands.

Ground-truth data collection: Spectral measurements were measured over seagrass beds at varying water depths using a GER 1500 and two units of Ocean Optics USB 2000+ spectroradiometers. The geographic coordinates of the location of the data collection are presented in the Table 2. Each of the USB 2000+ models was fitted with a fiber optic cable, one measured downwelling radiation and the other upwelling radiation. The data collected was instantaneously saved to computer and used to compute reflectance values. Water quality data were collected using YSI 6600 after the machine was fully calibrated. Photosynthetic Active Radiation (PAR) was also collected using LI-250A light meter. The PAR calibration value of -248.14 μm was to measure light just above the water level, then calibrated to a value of -327.54 μm to measure light just under the water surface, at 50cm and at 100cm. Water samples were also collected, and processed with 24 hours and used to determine dissolved organic carbon (DOC) and chlorophyll-*a* concentration.

Table 2. The geographic coordinates of the study sites where ground-truth data were collected.

SITE	COORDINATES	SITE NAME
1	30.3828N, 88.3983W	Middle Bay
2 & 2-1	30.3853N, 88.4006W	Middle Bay
3	30.3617N, 88.3988W	Grand Bay
4	30.3523N, 88.4093W	Jose Bay
5	30.3555N, 88.4108W	Jersey Bay

4.3 Characterization of depth-variant SAV signals

The spectral reflectance data of the common aquatic vegetation from the controlled (outdoor tanks) experimental setting were used to: (1) compare spectral reflectance characteristics of aquatic plants that are adapted to grow above water surface (emergent/floating vegetation) and below water surface (SAV); (2) document the effects of SAV in the composite upwelling energy from a water body; and (3) test if NDVI values for underwater plants can be improved if corrected for spectral attenuation caused by water.

Reflectance data were plotted against the wavelengths 400-900 nm. From the plot of the spectral data collected over healthy waterhyacinth, senescing waterhyacinth, submerged waterhyacinth, waterhyacinth flowers, emerged SAV, and SAV canopy just below water surface, the wavelength and the corresponding reflectance value (%) of each reflectance peaks and dips were observed and calculated. In order to see the effects of flooding on the reflectance, the spectral reflectance of flooded vegetation was subtracted from the spectral reflectance of healthy emerged vegetation for each plant type (waterhyacinth and SAV).

The spectral reflectance was averaged for the RED and NIR bands to simulate reflectance from satellites sensors of ASTER, SPOT 5, and LANDSAT 7 ETM+. NDVI values were then calculated for each depth using the averaged NIR and RED reflectance values. Spectral reflectance data collected over the black panel were subtracted from the SAV spectral reflectance collected at the comparable water depth to reduce the water effect (corrected for water effect). NDVI values were re-calculated using the corrected data.

4.4 Water effect modeling to extend the depth limit of SAV detection

The schematic experimental models are presented in Fig.1.

$$L_r = 0\%$$

$$L_b = 100\%$$

$$L_r = 0\%$$

$$L_b = 100\%$$

Figure 1. Schematic experimental tanks comparing the reflected upwelling energy from water with two different bottom types, a black panel and a white panel. L_i is the total incident light energy; L_s is the light reflected from the water surface; L_v is the volumetric reflectance (light energy scattered back from the water column); L_a is the light absorbed by the water column; L_r is the light energy reflected by the bottom; and L_b is the light energy absorbed by the bottom.

Fig.1(a) shows upwelling energy components from a water body with a black bottom (a hypothetical surface that absorbs 100% of the incoming light that transmits the water column and reaches the bottom); and Fig. 1(b) for a white bottom (a hypothetical surface that reflects 100% of the incoming light).

At a specific wavelength the incident light energy (L_i) at the water surface can be expressed as the following:

$$L_i = L_s + L_v + L_a + L_r + L_b \quad (1)$$

Where L_s is the light reflected from the water surface, L_v is the volumetric reflectance (light energy scattered back from the water column), L_a is the light absorbed by the water column, L_r is the light energy reflected by the bottom, and L_b is the light energy absorbed by the bottom. Although the volumetric reflectance (L_v) is depth-variance and the water surface reflectance (L_s) is independent of water depth changes, we combined these two terms into one term (L_w) for computational simplicity because L_s is a constant and does not modify the linear relationship between L_v and water depth. The equation (1) can be simplified as the following:

$$L_i = L_w + L_a + L_r + L_b \quad (2)$$

Dividing (2) by L_i

$$R_w + A_w + R_r + A_b = 1 \quad (3)$$

Where R_w is percent reflectance comprised of both water surface and water volumetric contributions; A_w is percent absorption that considers both upward and downward paths through the vertical water column; R_r is reflectance that is attributed to the reflection from the surface of black panel (% bottom reflectance); and A_b is absorption of the bottom panel. For an ideal black body, R_r equals 0 while for true white body, A_b equals 0.

In our experiment, the measured reflectance R_m above the water tank with the white bottom equals $R_w + R_r$

$$A_w + R_m = 1 = 100\% \quad (4)$$

and the measured reflectance R_m above the water tank with the black bottom equals R_w .

$$R_w = R_m \quad (5)$$

Using the A_w and R_w derived from equations (4)-(5), a function to estimate the corrected reflectance, R_c , measured from measured from any shallow water bodies for the water effects (the depth-dependent water volumetric scattering and water absorption) was developed.

$$R_c = f(R_m) \quad (6)$$

Note that R_c and R_m are functions of both wavelength and water depth. The absorption and water volumetric scattering for all the hyperspectral channels can be obtained by using equations (4) and (5). Regression analysis was applied to the data for both water absorption and volumetric scattering. The hyperbolic tangent function with a general form of

$$f(x) = a \tanh(\beta x) \quad (7)$$

was fitted in the regression to ensure a water impact of zero when water depth is 0 cm. The variable x is water depth in centimeters; and $f(x)$ represents either water absorption or water volumetric reflectance. The parameters a and β in equation (7) were determined by regressing

the experimental data for each spectral band, which produced a total of 315 pairs for either water absorption or volumetric scattering. The fitted function agreed well with the observation especially within the red and near infrared bands with the standard deviation values less than 6% of the mean values in most bands except at the short wavelength bands (400-470 nm).

4.5 Application of water correction algorithm in image data

The 2008 AISA data taken over Mission-Aransas NERR were used to testify the efficiency of the algorithm developed. A subset image (98 x116 pixels) that contains seagrass beds was selected and used in algorithm application. A spectral subset was also conducted to select the interested bands from 500 nm to 850 nm from the original 315 channels ranging from 401 nm to 981 nm; the short and long wavelength regions were removed because they contained substantial noises. Since the spatial variation of the water depth was not available for the area, a constant water depth of 40 cm was assumed for all pixels in the domain. To compare the differences of reflectance before and after correction via using the algorithm, some pixels in domain were chosen to denote vegetated substrate (SAV) and bare sandy substrate.

4.6 Data Compression for Hyperspectral Data

Since DCT and wavelets are well-known and widely used image compressions, and they are utilized at the international standards, JPEG and JPEG 2000, we studied JPEG and JPEG 2000's performance over two different types of remote sensing images. We collected two sets of test images each of which consists of 20 true color remote sensing images, to investigate how these two methods perform over the different image contents. Each test image from each test set was encoded and decoded with the JPEG and JPEG 2000 codecs at the compression ratios of 2:1, 5:1, 10:1, and 20:1, then the results were analyzed with standardized performance matrix in data compression.

The test images were selected from World Wind Central (WWC, <http://www.worldwindcentral.com>), a public center for downloading remote sensing images. All of the test images were color images consisting of three bands at the blue, green, and red wavelengths and of 600 by 600 pixels. As mentioned earlier, the first test set (Test set #1) contains 20 images of natural scenes, and the second set (Test set #2) contains 20 images of urban scenes. Fig. 2 shows two example images from each of the sets.

(a) An image from Test set #1

(b) An image from Test set #2

Figure 2: Images from the Two Test Sets

For JPEG lossy compression, Macromedia Fireworks was used, and for JPEG 2000 compression, JasPer (<http://www.ece.uvic.edu/~mdadams/jasper>) was used for encoding and decoding the images. Each image from the test sets was compressed at the ratios of 2:1, 5:1, 10:1, and 20:1 with Fireworks and JasPer separately, and was decoded back for a reconstructed image.

To measure the JPEG and JPEG 2000's performance over the test images, MSE and PSNR values were calculated for each set of encoding and decoding of the images. MSE is usually used to summarize the information in two different sequences (in our experiment, an image and a corresponding reconstructed image) and defined as follows:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2$$

where n is the number of pixels in the image, x_i is the i th pixel value in the original image, and \hat{x}_i is the i th pixel value in the reconstructed image. Thus, MSE indicates how much image degradation exists on a pixel-based level.

On the other hand, PSNR is used to measure the size of errors relative to the peak value of the input sequence and defined as follows:

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{MAX^2}{MSE} \right) dB$$

where MAX is the maximum pixel values of the original image. The PSNR and MSE values indicate the quality of reconstructed images: a higher PSNR and a smaller MSE value imply better quality. In general, reconstructed images with PSNR values greater than 30 dB are considered to be in good quality and acceptable to most image applications.

For the performance measure, PSNR and MSE were calculated with *imgcmp*, which is a library function provided by JasPer. *imgcmp* calculates the difference between two images by using one of the distortion metrics, such as PSNR, MSE, root mean squared error, peak absolute error, or mean absolute error. Since the test images were true color images, *imgcmp* produced three values representing the red, green, and blue for each test image, and thus, the three values were averaged for a single PSNR or MSE value.

4.7 Significant Hyperspectral Bands for Detecting SAV

We have used IDT (Priebe et al. 2004a; Priebe et al. 2004b) to study the hyperspectral data. IDT has shown that under certain conditions, the optimal strategy is a tree: an initial collection is used to select the bands (or features) for a subsequent collection, which in turn drives the next collection, and so on. In our experiments, multiple pairs of Principal Component Analysis (PAC) and clustering along with IDT constructed trees that define the spectral bands to collect, conditional on the results of previous collections.

We also studied Incomparable Sensors (Cowen et al. 1997; Marchette 2003), which is a method to compare observations taken under very different conditions or sensors. The method maps the observations into a space in which they can be compared. The mapping makes use of a pairing of observations, or sets of observations, and computing distances between the data and these sets. The distance then forms a nonlinear projection of the observations into a space in which all can be compared. Incomparable Sensors has shown that it works well for paired data where two sensors observed the same objects, data of similar objects (but not paired), semi-comparable data where some of the bands are overlapped, and the data that has no bands in common.

Since we need to study effects of water depth, turbidity, and vegetation, paired combinations of the 3 features were identified as shown in Table 3:

Table 3. Combinations of the Features

	Water Depth	Turbidity	Vegetation
C1	T	T	T
C2	T	T	F
C3	T	F	T
C4	T	F	F
C5	F	T	T
C6	F	T	F
C7	F	F	T
C8	F	F	F

* T refers to the case where the feature presents its effect, and F refers to the case where the effect doesn't exist (or can't be captured)

For example, G_A in (Fig. 3) shows the two cases where C7 indicates detectable vegetation effect on hyperspectral data from clear and shallow water, and C8 indicates observations from no vegetation under the same condition. By comparing C7 and C8, we expect to see vegetation effects on hyperspectral data.

Figure 3. Studying Vegetation, Depth, and Turbidity Effects

Furthermore, with the 4 groups of the cases and their combinations as shown in Fig.3, we also can study interactions among vegetation, depth, and turbidity effects. For instance, a study on depth effects according to Incomparable Sensors can be done with G_A and G_B : when bridge pixels are set to the observations of vegetation from C7 and C3, denoted by V_A and V_B respectively, then each observation from G_A and each observation from G_B can be compared with $d(x, V_A)$ and $d(y, V_B)$ where d refers to a distance measure, x refers to an observation from G_A , and y refers to an observation from G_B . The same process can be done with G_A and G_D to investigate how turbidity effects interact with depth effects. For these experiments, R language (<http://www.r-project.org>) has been used.

5 Findings/Results

5.1 Characterization of depth-variant SAV signals

Comparison of Spectral Reflectance Characteristics of Emergent Plants and SAV: Spectral reflectance (400-900 nm) of waterhyacinth and SAV are plotted together for comparison in Fig.4. Healthy waterhyacinth and emerged SAV showed the typical vegetation spectral reflectance pattern: the green reflectance peak at around 557 nm, red absorption near 660-670 nm, and the NIR peak (> 730 nm), but the reflectance values at the green and NIR peaks were significantly lower in emerged SAV (7.5% and 6.3% respectively) compared to those of waterhyacinth (23.7% and 76%). The red absorption by the plants pigments appear less in

emergent SAV than waterhyacinth, resulting in the relative higher reflectance at the red wavelength for emerged SAV (6.3%) than waterhyacinth (4.6%).

Figure 4: Spectral reflectance (%) of the floating waterhyacinth and submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV).

When submerged below water surface, the spectral reflectance for both waterhyacinth and SAV decreased at the green, red, and NIR regions. The reflectance was reduced to 5% (green), 3.6% (red), and 10% (NIR) for waterhyacinth when submerged; and the corresponding reflectance for SAV was 1.5%, 0.9%, and 3.5%. The magnitudes of reflectance reduction caused by submergence were comparable between waterhyacinth and SAV at green (79% reduction) and NIR (87% and 91% reduction), but the red reflectance was more significantly reduced in SAV (85% reduction) than in waterhyacinth (22% reduction). The maximum peak and the minimum dip wavelengths in the green and red reflectance were shifted to somewhat lower ranges (557nm \rightarrow 553 nm and 677nm \rightarrow 640 nm) in waterhyacinth.

The general flooding effects on the vegetation signals were similar to those observed in previous studies (Han and Rundquist 2003; Jackson et al. 2004; Beget and Di Bella 2007): reduced red absorption and NIR peak by vegetation. The near infrared reflectance shown as a reflectance plateau in terrestrial or in emergent plants became two peaks near at approximately 710-715nm and 810-815nm in the submerged plants due to the water absorption of the energy in between those two NIR peaks.

Since the upwelling signals over the black panel contain information on changes in the water column volume without the bottom reflectance (Fig. 1), the spectral reflectance of the black panel was subtracted from the spectral reflectance of the SAV at each comparable depth in order to test if the SAV signal can be extracted better if the water volume reflectance is removed. An example of the correction with the data from black panel is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: An example of the original reflectance of SAV compared the same data corrected with the black panel data at the same depth.

The NDVI values for SAV at each water depth calculated using the original spectral reflectance at the corresponding red and NIR regions are presented and compared with the NDVI calculated using the corrected spectral reflectance (SAV reflectance – black panel reflectance) are presented in Fig. 6. The NDVI values calculated with the original reflectance ranged 0.6-0.65 when the SAV canopy was at the water level, then they decreased linearly (slope of 0.013 NDVI/meter) with water depth increases in clear water. When corrected for water attenuation using the data values for senescing waterhyacinth, submerged waterhyacinth, and SAV canopy at water surface appear similar. Particularly, the effects of senescence and submergence on the vegetation reflectance were very similar even at the hyperspectral resolution. The purple/violet-colors of waterhyacinth flowers can also affect classification of the plants using NDVI during the peak flowering season because the relatively increased reflectance at red (Fig. 4) for the flowers results in lower NDVI values (0.5 as opposed to 0.8 or above for waterhyacinth leaves). These aspects should be considered when taking ground-truth measurements in order to reduce errors in image classification and delineation.

Figure 6: Water depth-induced changes in the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) values compared with the NDVI values calculated from the corrected reflectance (SAV reflectance – black panel reflectance) at the corresponding depths.

5.2 Water effect modeling to extend the depth limit of SAV detection

We applied the correction algorithm to the previously measured reflectance of SAV (*Myriophyllum aquaticum* and *Cabomba caroliniana*) at varying water depths to test if the algorithm enhances signals from underwater vegetation. We used several sets of SAV reflectance data; and the ones collected under different water turbidity conditions (0 and 6, NTU) on two separate days (6/14/2006 and 6/21/2007) over outdoor experimental tanks are presented. For each set of the data used, Coefficient of Variation (CV) and NDVI values were calculated for the original reflectance and the corrected reflectance for comparison. In order to calculate the NDVI values, the measured hyperspectral SAV reflectance was averaged for the red (630-690nm) and the NIR (760-900nm) wavelength regions to match the spectral bands of Landsat 7 ETM+. The parameters a and β utilized in equation (7) for the red and NIR bands were determined by averaging the two parameters through all channels within the red and NIR bands.

The measured and the corrected SAV reflectance curves are shown in Fig. 7. For the water with turbidity 0, the estimate of the reflectance has increased over all spectral regions after the correction. The percent reflectance increased due to the correction increased with water depth and also with wavelength. The percent reflectance increases ranged between 46-69% in the blue region (400-500 nm), 47-70% in the green (500-600 nm), 50-74% in the red (600-700 nm), and 98-115% in the NIR (700-900 nm) (Figs 7(a) and 7(b)). A similar pattern was observed for the data collected from water with 6 NTU using the coefficient values (R_w and A_w) derived from our experiment using 0 NTU (Figs. 7(c) and 7(d)), but the NIR correction had a larger variation with the percent reflectance increases ranging from 60-533%.

Figure 7. Spectral reflectance (%) of Submerged Aquatic Vegetation (SAV) (a) Measured at varying water depths and at turbidity of 0 NTU; (b) Corrected for water absorption and scattering at varying water depths at turbidity of 0 NTU; (c) Measured at varying water depths at turbidity of 6 NTU; and (d) Corrected for water absorption and scattering at varying water depths at turbidity of 6 NTU.

The depth-induced variation in spectral reflectance is expected to be reduced in data corrected for water absorption and scattering, which was evidenced by the decreased Coefficient of Variation (CV) values in the NIR of the 0 NTU water (Fig. 8(a)) and in the 450-900 nm of the 6 NTU water (Fig. 8(b)). NDVI values, calculated from the spectral reflectance integrated to the red (630-690 nm) and the NIR (760-900 nm) bands of the Landsat 7 ETM+, increased at all depths in both 0 and 6 NTU waters (Figs. 8(c) and 8(d)).

Figure 8. (a) Coefficient of Variation (CV) of spectral reflectance (%) of Submerged Aquatic Vegetation (SAV) measured at varying water depths at turbidity of 0 NTU and (b) Same for 6 NTU. (c) Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) values calculated from the spectral reflectance (%) of SAV measured at varying water depths at turbidity of 0 NTU and (d) Same for 6 NTU (d).

5.3 Application of the model in image data

Fig. 9 is the NDVI values computed through the uncorrected (a) and corrected reflectance values (b). An assumption was made that the highest value of NDVI represent vegetation pixel whereas the lowest NDVI is bare ground. The dark-filled circles represent bare surface under water, and cross-circles denote potential vegetation. Total 8 pixels for bare surface and 10 for SAV were determined. Fig 10. shows the spectral profile of the averaged reflectance values for bare ground (a) and SAV (b).

a

b

Figure 9. NDVI values computed using the uncorrected (a) and corrected reflectance values (b). The dark-filled circles represent bare surface under water, and cross-circles denote potential vegetation.

a.

b.

Figure 10. Spectral profiles of the averaged reflectance values for bare ground (a) and SAV (b).

5.4 Data Compression for Hyperspectral Data

From the experiment, JPEG reconstructed images at compression ratios (CRs) of 10:1 and 20:1 contain the most notable distortions. The JPEG reconstructed image at CR of 20 from Test set #1 suffers most from blocking and coloring artifacts, which would cause problems in biophysical

modeling. It also appears to have a slightly worse quality when compared to the JPEG reconstructed image from Test set #2 at the same compression ratio.

With respect to PSNR values, most of the JPEG 2000 reconstructed images produced values over 30 dB, indicating that they were in good quality. In contrast, most of the JPEG reconstructed images produced values less than 30 dB, which indicated the quality may not be acceptable in image applications. Besides, JPEG reconstructed images at CR of 10 and 20 produced significant coloring artifacts. The resulting images and the PSNR values show that both compression methods worked better for the image from Test set #2, and JPEG 2000 worked better compared to JPEG. Table 4 summarizes the average MSE and PSNR values at the different compression ratios from the two test sets.

Table 4. Average MSE and PSNR Values from the Two Test Sets

	CR	JPEG				JPEG 2000			
		2:1	5:1	10:1	20:1	2:1	5:1	10:1	20:1
MSE	Test set #1	43.66	115.52	266.79	434.63	0.00032	1.88	12.24	77.45
	Test set #2	37.16	111.16	273.87	406.09	0.00032	1.87	10.09	35.29
PSNR	Test set #1	32.46	27.98	24.16	22.26	84.99	46.12	38.32	32.39
	Test set #2	32.56	27.79	23.88	22.21	84.35	45.61	38.36	32.90

As seen in Fig. 11, JPEG 2000's PSNR value dropped quickly as the compression ratios increased. Also, the PSNR value differences between JPEG and JPEG 2000 coding decreased as the compression ratios increased.

Figure 11. PSNR Values in Summary

5.5 Significant Hyperspectral Bands for Detecting SAV

We applied IDT over the two data sets from black panel and vegetation on a black panel, presented in Section 4.1, to study depth and vegetation effects over the hyperspectral data. A total of 315 wavelength bands starting from 400 to 900 nm were collected from the depth of 5

cm up to 40 cm with the 5 cm difference along the depth. Fig 12. shows the reflectance at each depth of the vegetation on a black panel.

Figure 12. Reflectance of Vegetation on a Black Panel

The two test sets produced 5040 observations, 2520 observations from each, and we set 3 features for the IDT process: reflectance, wavelength bands, and depth. After PCA, a model-based clustering was conducted over the PCA results to identify significant wavelength bands for detecting SAV. From the 1st iteration of the IDT process, the result shows that the bands indicated in Fig. 13 are significant based on the observations from the cluster that contains only vegetation. The figure also shows a pattern among the bands as the depth increases. After the 2nd iteration, about 95% of the observations were meaningfully clustered, and Fig. 14 shows the second most significant bands for detecting SAV based on the clusters constructed from the 2nd iteration. They also present a pattern among the selected bands.

Figure 13. Most Significant Wavelength Bands for Detecting SAV

Figure 14. Second Most Significant Wavelength Bands for Detecting SAV

5.6 Extending Reflectance Data by Radial Basis Function Interpolation

Our goal here was to study submerged aquatic vegetation and how it grows under certain conditions. In our controlled experiments, we measured the amount of light energy being reflected from the submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV) at varying water depths. Since our experiments only covered depths between a fixed range due to equipment limitations, we employed Radial Basis Function Interpolation (RBF) to extrapolate reflectance values at deeper depth. Our aim was to extend the results found in the controlled experiments as far as possible. The reason for this is to find at which depth there will be enough light for photosynthesis. This critical depth is the hypothetical location of SAV. We were able to extrapolate (using thin-plate spline RBF) reflectance data up to a depth 100 cm (Fig.15). starting from reflectance data between 0 cm. and 70 cm. We chose the thin-plate spline RBF because it outperformed other basis functions (multiquadric, gaussian, cubic, etc.). Our attempt to iteratively extend data by using previously extrapolated data and experimental data as new training data failed to provide realistic reflectance profiles.

Figure 15. 3-D interpolation of the experimental data using thin-plate RBF.

5.7 Detection of Local Maximum and Minimum Values of the Reflectance Profile

The reflectance profile of SAV has local extrema that are important in selecting bands for use in image analysis. Amongst local extrema, there are some that result from noisy experimental data. In order to mitigate the effect of noise on the location of extrema, we first filter our experimental data using the Savitsky-Golay Filter (Fig. 16). The filtered data is then interpolated using the appropriate RBF. This interpolated data is used to compute first-order derivatives. We then found the zeros of the first derivative. These zeros are candidates for local extrema. In order to discriminate the actual local extrema from these zeros, we apply the first derivative test.

Figure 16. Automatic detection of local minima in wavelengths between 400 and 900 nm.

5.8 Effects of Water on the Vegetation Profile

In order to decompose the SAV profile into pure water and pure vegetation profiles to find the contribution of each member in the mixture. We employed experimental reflectance data from submerged vegetation, terrestrial vegetation, and pure water (Fig. 17). We formulate the problem as a signal unmixing problem that we solve using Lagrange Multiplier Method and Quadratic Programming Method. The two methods provide reasonable results. However, the Quadratic Programming approach allowed us to enforce the constraint that the contributions must be positive in order to have physical meaning.

Figure 17. Mixing of vegetation signal with clear water signal.

6 Analysis, Products and Discussion

6.1 Characterization of depth-variant SAV signals

As demonstrated in previous studies (Venugopal 2002; Shekede et al. 2008), our results support that NDVI can serve as a good indicator to delineate healthy waterhyacinth and other emergent/floating water plants because of the high reflectance in the NIR regions and low red reflectance (Fig. 4), the spectral responses that resemble the terrestrial vegetation spectral signals. Our results also indicate NDVI can be used to distinguish and classify floating plants by their health status (Fig. 4), but confusing classification results may occur as the NDVI values for senescing waterhyacinth, submerged waterhyacinth, and SAV canopy at water surface appear similar. Particularly, the effects of senescence and submergence on the vegetation reflectance were very similar even at the hyperspectral resolution (Fig. 4). The purple/violet-colors of waterhyacinth flowers can also affect classification of the plants using NDVI during the peak flowering season because the relatively increased reflectance at red (Fig. 4) for the flowers results in lower NDVI values. These aspects should be considered when taking ground-truth measurements in order to reduce errors in image classification and delineation.

Submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV) plants that are adapted to underwater life had lower NDVI values than those of floating plants even when emerged above water surface. The red reflectance for the emerged SAV was higher than healthy waterhyacinth, which indicates lower red absorption by the plant pigments in SAV; and the NIR reflectance was also significantly lower than that of waterhyacinth. This is probably due to the SAV's lower chlorophyll content of the leaves per unit of tissue and weight (Hemminga and Duarte 2000) and the higher water contents in and on SAV leaves. One interesting factor is that SAV below water surface had the higher NDVI values than submerged waterhyacinth at the same depth, which probably explains the red absorption by waterhyacinth is more significantly affected by submergence compared to SAV that is adapted to utilize the red color more efficiently in submerged conditions.

NDVI appears to be useful in delineating SAV canopy at the water surface (NDVI values close to 0.6), but the values decreased linearly with water depth increases, becoming ineffective for underwater vegetation detection even at the depth of 0.3 m (Fig. 6). However, the NDVI values significantly increased at all depths that we tested (0.1 – 0.5 m) when corrected for water attenuation using the data obtained from the black panel, indicating the index values can be used for studies of SAV that from canopies near water surface if information on spectral reflectance attenuation caused by water volume increases is collected in the field and used to correct the original spectral reflectance data.

The importance of this research is linked to the need for mapping the distribution, composition, and abundance of aquatic vegetation in shallow inland and coastal waters using satellite images. Aquatic plants provide food to aquatic organisms, serve as nursery habitats, help reduce shoreline erosion, and influence the supply of oxygen in water. However, fast growing aquatic plants especially free-floating or floating-leaved plants of inland water bodies can become invasive by outcompeting native species. Therefore, information on aquatic vegetation distribution, composition, and abundance is widely used as an indicator of aquatic environmental quality; and the improved mapping capability for those plants will enhance the ability to assess underwater habitat changes.

6.2 Water effect modeling to extend the depth limit of SAV detection

Approximately 90% of the remote sensing signals from a water body that are detected by a sensor at the top of the atmosphere are contributed by the atmosphere and water surface (Gitelson and Kondratyev 1991). In this study, the atmospheric effect was not considered; and we combined the water surface and water column properties in order to extract the signals only coming from bottom and corrected the signals to reflectance at the water surface. Previous studies modeled absorption and molecular scattering of pure water and water column constituents from diffuse light attenuation coefficients that have been estimated based on field measured underwater irradiance (Smith and Baker 1981; Maritorea and Guillocheau 1996). However, field measured vertical light attenuation coefficient (K_d) is affected by the bottom substrate type and albedo (Boss and Zaneveld 2003, Werdell and Roesler 2003); and the coefficients can be applied more successfully in deep water studies ($>3\text{m}$) (Hedley and Mumby 2003). The algorithm in this study to remove water absorption and scattering was derived from controlled measurements at a much finer scale. Application of the algorithm significantly improved the vegetation signals, especially in the NIR region (Fig. 7), although we included only the clear water effect in our experiment. As mentioned earlier, the conventional vegetation indices cannot be effectively used for plants that grow underwater even in shallow waters of less than 1m (Beget and Di Bella 2007; Cho *et al.* 2008). We believe the experimentally-driven algorithm will improve mapping capabilities of seagrass beds and invasive aquatics of shallow coastal and inland water environments.

6.3 Application of the model in image data

The application of the experimentally driven algorithm in aerial hyperspectral data successfully restored the water effects (Figs. 9 and 10). Prior to the correction, both the bare areas and vegetated areas showed the low NIR reflectance (Fig. 10), which makes it hard to classify the seagrass beds when using the conventional clustering techniques. The correction using our empirical algorithm significantly restored the NIR reflectance of the seagrass beds (Fig. 10), which will improve the underwater classification capability.

6.4 Data Compression for Hyperspectral Data

As shown in Table 4, images from Test set #1 (natural scenes) produced higher MSE values than images from Test set #2 (urban scenes) in JPEG and JPEG 2000 coding. Specifically, at the compression ratio of 20 in JPEG 2000 compression, the average MSE value of Test set #1 was over twice larger than that of Test set #2. This difference was probably due to the slow changing nature of continuous tone within the natural scenes: high frequencies within the regions were quantized to become zeros or almost zeros so that they were not delivered during the encoding process. Therefore, according to the MSE values, both JPEG and JPEG 2000 appeared to perform better for images of non-continuous objects.

The PSNR value differences between JPEG and JPEG 2000 coding decreased as the compression ratios increased (Fig. 11). These indicate that the significance of JPEG 2000's compression becomes obscured as the compression ratios increase. According to the PSNR values, it is clear that JPEG 2000 works much better than JPEG at any compression ratio: JPEG 2000 produced PSNR values greater than 30 dB for all the test images in average; JPEG produced PSNR values less than 30 dB for most of the cases, except the cases with the compression ratio of 2:1. This result shows that the wavelet-based compression method (JPEG 2000) produces better performance in encoding the remote sensing images than the DCT-based compression method (JPEG). However, JPEG 2000's wavelet-based compression utilizes much

more complicated process, and its significance becomes obscured at high compression ratios, and thus in the case where processing overheads matter, and low compression is acceptable, JPEG can be still considered as an alternative.

As shown in Fig. 18, we also observed from our IDT experiments on hyperspectral data that about half of the features (or dimensions) can represent the data. Namely, about a half of the components from PCA present significant differences among the all components. This conforms to “Curse of Dimensionality”, and thus, if a data reduction produces about a half of the original data, then a lossless compression can be an alternative: since a lossless compression can achieve a compression ratio of 2, the resulting size of the data would be around one-quarter of the original data.

Figure 18. Data Reduction with PCA

6.5 Significant Hyperspectral Bands for Detecting SAV

As seen in Fig. 13, wavelengths from 515 to 640 nm and from 695 to 900 nm were most significant in detecting SAV. The figure also shows that as the depth increased, more of 600-level and less of 800-level bands were utilized. In addition, as presented in Fig. 14, the remaining bands were utilized as well in detecting SAV during the 2nd iteration. Among the wavelength bands, more of 850 to 900 bands were utilized as the depth increased.

As aforementioned, after the 2nd iteration, about 95% of the vegetation observations were meaningfully clustered. The remaining 5% of the observations were misplaced, and most of them came from the wavelength range of between 400 and 480 nm. This indicates that the corresponding wavelengths may attenuate the vegetation effect. We also found that each cluster containing only vegetation consists of about the same number of observations from each depth, which implies that the depth differences do not have much impact among the observations. All of these findings thus indicate that we need to fully utilize the wavelengths in detecting SAV, and the depth effect may not be significant under certain conditions, which will be further investigated with other data sets.

7 Conclusion

Our study suggest that: (1) The experimentally driven algorithm significantly improved the vegetation signals, especially in the NIR regions; (2) The algorithm also improved mapping capabilities of dense seagrass beds in shallow, clear water; and (3) It will be applicable in invasive aquatics of coastal and inland water environments if water color effects are included. In most of our data analysis, we noted that noise markedly affects our inference. In order to address this issue, we need better filtering, experimental data, and robust models.

8 Future Work

With collected experimental, ground-truth, and image data, we will further investigate hyperspectral bands for detecting SAV based on our proposed approach. By utilizing the features of the experimental data that have been collected under carefully designed and controlled environments, we expect to study effects of the features on hyperspectral bands and the interactions among them. Furthermore, the resulting hyperspectral bands will be adapted in developing compression methods for hyperspectral and image data. We will also study and implement Incomparable Sensors, including distance measures, along with IDT so that all of our datasets can be fully explored in facilitating the development of proposed algorithms. All the resulting artifacts from the process will help us better understand the effects and characteristics of the data.

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Tab 1: Publications

M.S. Theses

1. Gaye, G. 2011. The Enhanced Water Correction Module in ENVI. M.S. Project, May 11. Jackson State University, Jackson, Mississippi
2. Washington, M. 2011. Numerical solutions of the 2D Navier-Stokes equations. MS Thesis, May 11. Jackson State University, Jackson, Mississippi

Full Publications (* indicates student author)

3. Cho, H.J., D. Mishra, P. Kirui*, and J. Wood*. (submitted; invited book chapter) *Remote Sensing of Submerged Aquatic Vegetation*. **Remote Sensing**/Book 2, ISBN 979-953-307-876-1.
4. Mishra, D., H.J. Cho, S. Ghosh, C. Downs, A. Fox, P. Merani, P. Kirui, N. Jackson, and S. Mishra. (in Revision) Post-spill State of the Marsh: Impact of the Gulf of Mexico Oil Spill on the Health and Productivity of Louisiana Salt Marshes. *Remote Sensing of Environment*
5. Gibel Gaye*, Hyunju Kim, and Hyun J. Cho. 2011. Utilizing the significant spectral bands for image outputs for SAV from the water effect correction module. Proceeding of the 2011 WORLDCOMP
6. Washington*, M., C. P. Kirui*, Cho, H.J., and Wafo-Soh. 2011. Data-driven Correction for Light Attenuation in Shallow Waters. *Remote Sensing Letters* 3(4) 335-342, ISSN 2150-7058.
7. Lu, D* and Cho, H.J. 2011. An improved water-depth correction algorithm for seagrass mapping using hyperspectral data. *Remote Sensing Letters* 2(2): 91-97.
8. Cho, H.J. and D. Lu*. 2010. A water-depth correction algorithm for submerged vegetation spectra. *Remote Sensing Letters* 1(1): 29-35.
9. Gibel Gaye*, Hyunju Kim, and Hyun J. Cho. 2010. A Study on Spectral Bands for Detecting Submerged Aquatic Vegetation from Hyperspectral Data, *Proceedings of ADMI 2010* (in CD-Rom), 4 pages
10. Cho, H.J., D. Lu*, and M. Washington*. 2009. Water correction algorithm application for underwater vegetation signal improvement. *Proceedings of the 2009 MS Water Resource Conference* 152-155.
11. Shayron Nicoles*, Hyunju Kim, Ali A. Humos, and Hyun Jung Cho. 2009. A Performance Evaluation on Discrete Cosine Transform and Wavelet-based Compression Methods for Remote Sensing Images based on Image Content. *Proceedings of the 2009 Geoinformatics*. (in CD-Rom)
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Abstracts

1. Kirui, P.*, M. Washington*, G. Gaye*, and H.J. Cho. 2010. Depth-induced Variations in Hyperspectral Reflectance for Optical Water Quality Studies. AL-MS Bays and Bayous Symposium. 12/1 – 12/2, 2010. Mobile, AL.
2. Washington, M*, D. Lu, and H.J. Cho. 2010. A Water-Depth Correction Algorithm for Seagrass Mapping Using Hyperspectral Data. AL-MS Bays and Bayous Symposium. 12/1 – 12/2, 2010. Mobile, AL.

3. Kirui, P. and H.J. Cho. 2010. Depth-induced Variations in Hyperspectral Reflectance for Optical Water Quality Studies. Seventh International Symposium on Recent Advances in Environmental Health Research. Sept 12-15, 2010. Jackson, MS.
4. Nica, C. and H.J. Cho. 2010. Study of Seagrass Beds at Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve, Mississippi. Seventh International Symposium on Recent Advances in Environmental Health Research. Sept 12-15, 2010. Jackson, MS.
5. Lu, A. and H.J. Cho. 2010. Aquatic Plants of Mississippi Gulf Coast. Seventh International Symposium on Recent Advances in Environmental Health Research. Sept 12-15, 2010. Jackson, MS
6. Cho, H.J. and D. Lu. 2009. Spectral algorithm for improved submerged aquatic vegetation signals. The 2009 Coastal and Estuarine Research Federation. 11/1/2009- 11/6/2009. Portland, OR
7. Washington, M. * and H.J. Cho. 2009. Development of water correction algorithm for underwater vegetation signals. Sixth International Symposium on Recent Advances in Environmental Health Research, Sept 13-16, 2009, Jackson, MS.
8. Washington, M. * and H.J. Cho. 2009. Development of water correction algorithm for underwater vegetation signals. The 2009 Mississippi Water Conference, Aug 5-7, 2009, Tunica, MS.
9. Nicoles, S., H.Kim, A. Humos, and H.J. Cho. 2009. A performance evaluation on DCT and Wavelet-based Compression methods for remote sensing images based on image content. Geoinformatics 2009. Washington D.C.
10. Cho, H.J. Role of Remote Sensing Research and Education in Intelligence Studies. The 2009 TSU PCAEIS (Pilot Center for Academic Excellence in Intelligence Studies) Spring Academic Colloquium. Apr 14, 2009. Tennessee State University, Nashville, TN. (Invited Seminar)
11. P. Kirui* and Cho, H.J. and 2009. Classification of airborne hyperspectral data for shallow estuarine seagrass beds. Annual Conference of Mississippi Academy of Sciences. February 26-27, 2009. Olive Branch, MS (First place best student oral presentation).
12. Cho, H.J. and Marvin Washington*. 2009. Multi-spectral vegetation index for floating and canopy-forming aquatic vegetation. Annual Conference of Mississippi Academy of Sciences. February 26-27, 2009. Olive Branch, MS
13. Cho, H.J. 2008. Hyperspectral analysis for improved image classification of shallow estuarine submerged aquatic vegetation. Gulf Estuarine Research Society. Nov 5-7, 2008. Lindy Boggs International conference center, New Orleans, Louisiana
14. Cho, H.J. 2008. Experimental Approach to classify shallow estuarine waters using hyperspectral data. Alabama and Mississippi Bays and Bayous Symposium. October 28-29, 2008. Mississippi Coast Coliseum and Convention Center, Biloxi, MS. Paper published in *the Proceedings of the 2008 Bays and Bayous Symposium*: 126-127.
15. Natarajan, H*. and H.J. Cho. 2008. Effects of water depth and turbidity on spectral signature of submerged aquatic vegetation. Alabama and Mississippi Bays and Bayous Symposium. October 28-29, 2008. Mississippi Coast Coliseum and Convention Center, Biloxi, MS. Abstract published in *the Proceedings of the 2008 Bays and Bayous Symposium*: 122.

Tab 2: Students Supported

For annual/final reports, this tab, which starts on a new page, shows in tabular form every student supported during the reporting period.

Name	Graduate/Undergraduate	Degree Seeking	Status
Marvin Washington	Graduate	M.S. in Mathematics	Thesis defended, Graduated, Enrolled in the Aerospace Engineering Ph.D. Program at Penn State
Gibel Gaye	Graduate	M.S. in Computer Science	M.S. Final Project defended, Graduated
Philemon Kirui	Graduate	Ph.D. in Environmental Science	Enrolled Dissertation Title: Hyperspectral remote sensing for shallow water resources